

Part of

Characterisation of fungal cell wall architecture using solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy at fast spinning regime

Description

Electronic data

Description

The detailed data management plan for this project.

Researchers

Alons Lends (orcid:0000-0001-7883-613X)

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Characterisation of fungal cell wall architecture using solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy at fast spinning regime/ No Izp-2023/1-0312

Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

4

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

no I haven't.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

To other scientists in the field of NMR and biophysics.

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

doi

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

Yes

Date and sample names

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

In order to access the NMR data, programs like Bruker Topspin, CcpNmr and NMRPipe are necessary. All these computer programs have free of charge academic licences.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Academic Free License 3.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2034-05-31

Ten years is a typical life time of NMR consoles.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Alons Lends (orcid:0000-0001-7883-613X)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Powered by

